

Gender sensitivity in physical education classes in one state college

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ABSTRACT

Gender sensitivity is a process by which individuals are made mindful of how sexual orientation plays a critical parcel in life through overseeing others. This study aims to determine gender sensitivity in a physical education class in one state college. It employs a descriptive type of research. The respondents are the Physical Education students taking up P.E.102 and P.E.224. In this study, the mean and t-test were used as statistical tools. Study shows that P.E. 102 (Rhythmic Activities) classes are female-dominated with a strong willingness to explore their talents and skills, while males have limited participation due to reservations. Moreover, P.E.224 (Team Sports) is male-dominated where males showed too much interest in ballgames, while females are reserved and less motivated. Females needed more time for training to master certain skills. Moreover, the study's results showed that there is no distinguishable difference in the degree of gender sensitivity in Physical Education Classes as perceived by the students when taken as a whole and when grouped according to sex. Therefore, it is recommended that teachers of Physical Education classes should develop a method that is the interactive type to increase gender sensitivity among students. The development of instructional intervention by the faculty and administration to increase awareness of gender issues should be encouraged as mandated.

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INTRODUCTION

According to the Commission on Higher Education (CHED, 2014) the term "gender equality" refers to the favor of both male and female parity, in recognizing their full potential to contribute to and benefit from development outcomes, in their rights to appreciate fair treatment, and with the state acknowledging that all people are free and equal in their dignity and equality. When both genders value the same rights and opportunities across all spheres of society, as well as their unique needs and aspirations are equally valued and favored, gender balance is achieved.

In 2006, the World Economic Forum unveiled the Global Gender Gap Index another system that captures the greatness and scope of gender-based aberrations or national sexual orientation gaps in financial, political, education, and health criteria. This list influences the result of country improvement.

Gender and Development (GAD) is a relatively new paradigm. It is not surprising that only a few in the government or even in an educational institution, have enough knowledge, about it. Development is everybody's concern; however, certain conditions in society generate inequality in opportunities. Gender stereotypes, preconceptions, and interpretations put men and women through situations that restrict what they can do and who they can be, which limits their chances of leading fulfilling lives. It is therefore a must to understand our role regardless of age, sex, religion, or ethnicity in this so-called development.

International Educational for All (EFA); Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW); Millennium Development Goals (MDG); Magna Carta for Women, the Women in Country's Development Act, the Convention on the Rights of the Child, and RA 7877, the Anti-Sexual Harassment Law, are a few examples of GAD legal requirements.

To reinforce the teaching that prepares and teaches experts, gender disparities in instruction must be tended to. Educational Institutions have to be compelled to work together to guarantee that equal opportunities exist for both genders to pursue their goals. This requires going past equality, or only numerical adjustment among gender understudies and experts, to a more complex concept of balance in which youthful gender have equal access to tutoring and openings, and educational programs and approaches to instructing are not gender-biased (Beasley, 2006).

Schools, as institutions, are not impenetrable to outside variables driving sexual orientation (Kariuki, 2019). Physical Education is an avenue to express oneself for it gives opportunities to exercise maximum potential to become a productive and happy person for life. It aims to play a key role in educational opportunities in improving the social scenario.

Gender issues have always been central to physical education (Murphy, Dionigi, & Litchfield, 2014). These issues highly influence the perception and development of males, females, and children during their school years.

According to Everhart and Pemberton (2001), Men and boys have different sporting backgrounds than women and girls do. Sports have historically and traditionally been dominated by men. The data support the hypothesis that gender bias in sports is caused due to the gaps between male and female sports cultures and values, as well as the distinct sports' histories and traditions. During Ancient Olympics, women are not allowed to participate because they are considered lower-class citizens, unlike men who are regarded as first-class citizens. As we look at history, boys were trained to become war-like individuals to defend the state while girls were trained for graces.

Boys still outnumber girls in physical education, and teachers are known to support boys more (Scantlebury, 2009). Along with how teaching and learning experiences are perceived differently by men and women, they also have an impact on how physical education is planned and conducted in schools. Single-sex (all male or all female) or co-ed physical education classes are both possible (mixed grouping).

Despite the presence of mixed classes, it is going to be difficult to compare the performance of boys and girls because they use different grading systems. Furthermore, grades do not solely reflect performance because teachers consider students' time, investment (e.g., practice, quiz,) and overall improvement. Boys have been found to outperform girls in these areas (Flintoff, Fitzgerald, & Scraton, 2007). The perception that these differences are caused by biologically natural factors is one potential explanation. Males develop their physical capacities more than females during pubescent development. Males, therefore, perform better than females in motor tasks that call for strength or speed after puberty (Clément-Guillotin et al., 2012).

It is still true that male sports enjoy greater prestige than female sport because of traditional coaches and mass media that gives more stature to male sports rather than female in the center of popularity.

The gap between males and females has existed over the years. It exists in the home, schools, and workplaces. It is common knowledge here in the Philippines that men are considered the breadwinner of the family and women are preferred to be at home primarily to take care of the husband and the children. In terms of work, men are paid more than women because it is believed that men can do tougher jobs better compared to women. In education and sports, men are considered more competitive than women. In 1910, girls' basketball was introduced which contradicted the belief of many conservative Filipinos. Their perception of appropriate female behavior appears to be off, which discourages women from participating in sports (Wilhelmsen, 2012). Taking on gender inequality is a challenge for the modern society and the educational system. Therefore, schools and teachers at all levels have a crucial role to play in raising a future generation that is sensitive to gender issues.

In one state college, ideological colonization of gender stereotyping that girls are weak in doing sports activities limits their participation seems to prevail. In some of the researcher's classes in particular, which are boys-dominated, girls become uncomfortable when boys display power and strength. However, in girls-dominated classes, boys also show hesitation to participate. In doing group activity they prefer to group themselves with same-sex for they are freer to express themselves. It was noted that when in a competition a girl's involvement as a player/athlete usually becomes the reason for the team's loss.

Based on the researcher's interview with colleagues teaching P.E. classes, it was pointed out that P.E. 102 (Rhythmic Activities) classes are female-dominated with a strong willingness to explore their talents and skills, while males have limited participation due to reservations. Moreover, P.E. 224 (Team Sports) is male-dominated where males showed too much interest in ballgames, while females are reserved and less motivated. Females needed more time for training to master certain skills.

With all these observations, there is, therefore, a great need for imperative study on this area-gender sensitivity in Physical Education Classes.

The goal of the study:

The investigation's main aim was to establish:

1. The degree to which gender is sensitive in Physical Education Classes as perceived by the students in one state college when taken as a whole and when they are grouped according to sex.
2. When individuals are grouped by sex, is there an observable difference in the degree of gender sensitivity?

Hypothesis:

This hypothesis was formulated to answer the problem:

1. When students at one state college are divided into groups based on sex, there is no observable difference in the degree of gender sensitivity they perceive in Physical Education.

The framework of the Study

The idea of gender sensitivity, which is essential for development, served as the foundation for the formulation of this research problem. Gender Schema Theory discusses gender role identification. According to the gender schema theory, children construct a visual picture of what distinguishes males from females by observing people in their environment. As a person develops, these schemas become increasingly ingrained in how they view themselves, support how they find and assimilate new information that they deem pertinent to the schema, and change over time (Seymour, Reid, & Bloom, 2009).

Furthermore, Society shapes the desires of people and situational results through generalizations and standards. In case the standard does not happen, people may become uneasy. As such, the clarification for construction hypothesis clarifies how thought forms relate to life in society. People are slanted to handle information based on a person's gender, even if certain actions are considered inappropriate for either sex or the gender of the person. According to results, men responded more favorably to female competitors who agreed with sexual orientation stereotypes held by their don, while women preferred control of female competitors. In any case, sexism in sports continues to be firmly entrenched in people's mentalities even after being exposed to a picture at odds with stereotypes about sexual orientation in that sport.

Along with entrenching gender stereotypes, the educational system as well reinforces societal norms. (Clément-Guillotin et al., 2012) It is claimed that the majority of teachers held cultural norms about gender and used sexual identity techniques in the classroom. Teachers are unaware of, and deny, experiencing different understandings of men and women. The results reveal a big difference between men and women. teachers' gender stereotype beliefs, attitudes, and practices.

According to Mahoney (2012), gender preconceptions continue to make it difficult for women to hold military leadership posts, particularly in college Reserve Officers' Training Corps (ROTC) training programs. In a largely male military context, the social construction of sexual orientation in attaining a balance of gentility and manliness. Oftentimes, female cadets assume their workload has been twice as demanding as that of their peers, however, sexual orientation reliably underscored their achievements and administration. The greatest leaders among female cadets were those who understood the patriarchal military values. The premise of this theory, girls and boys are reluctant to participate in activities that require specific sexes and are afraid to be misjudged Basketball is a good example of this. Playing basketball is a male-dominated activity if a female will play, she will be judged as a lesbian. Same with dancing class or gymnastics which is girl dominant activity; if a boy joins, he will be judged as gay. Activating negative stereotyping by society affects individual performance.

The above-mentioned, are concepts, rationale, and justifications for addressing its problem of gender inequality. In this premise, this study seeks to identify the participation patterns of the students at that state college. perceive the degree of gender sensitivity in physical education. The variables are male and female, taken as a whole and taken according to sex. Figure 1 shows the schematic diagram of the theoretical structure of the research

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The type of research employed in this study was descriptive. In the realm of education, this is the most commonly used research design. It describes the nature of a situation at a specific moment in time, primarily through questionnaires, interviews, and observation. It portrays accurately the selected characteristics of the respondents under study and provides the necessary background for the development of the hypothesis. Utilizing this method, the primary goal is to describe the nature of the circumstance as it stands at the time of the study. One of the descriptive designs is a survey. The census on intangibles, which deals with constructs based on an indirect measure, is one of its classifications (Ardalez, 2008).

Research Locale

One State College is located on the National Highway, Brgy. Old Sagay, Sagay City in the northern part of Negros Occidental. It is a state college, a non-sectarian, non-profit institution, and a non-expensive cost college offering quality education.

The Population:

This study's participants were the (449) Four hundred forty-nine students comprising (422) Four hundred seventy-two Physical Education 102 (Rhythmic Activities) of BSE, BSBA, and BSIT and (27) twenty-seven P.E.224 (Team Sports) students of One State College, 2nd semester Academic Year 2014-2015.

Table 1. Distribution of the Respondent of the Study.

Course	Male	Female	Total
BSBA I-A	5	35	40
BSBA-B	5	41	46
BSBA –D	3	42	45
BSBA-E	8	37	45
BSED –A	9	41	50
BSED –E	12	38	50
BSEDII-A	8	19	27
BSIT –E	20	23	43
BSIT-G	26	34	60
BSIT-F	20	23	43
Total	116	333	449

The table shows that out of 449 respondents, 116 are male, and 333 are female.

Sampling Design and Technique

The study's subjects were 212 Physical Education students. Slovincs' formula was used to determine the respondents. The stratification of a population into smaller groups, known as strata, helps to calculate the sample size. In stratified random sampling, groups are created based on shared traits or characteristics among the participants. A random sample is drawn from each stratum in a quantity proportional to its size relative to the population. To create a random sample, these strata subsets are then combined. A fishbowl or lottery technique was used to allow everyone to be drawn out as respondents after determining the proportion of the sample size.

Table 2. Respondents' profiles when grouped according to Sex.

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	55	26.87
Female	157	73.13
Total	212	100

When grouped according to sex, out of 212 respondents, 55, or 26.87 percent were male, and 157 or 73.13 percent were females. The data showed that seventy percent of the respondents were female.

Data Gathering Instruments

The researcher used the survey questionnaire consisting of two parts: Part I is the respondent's profile and part II deals with three (3) aspects: Learners, Curriculum Content and Pedagogy, Planning, Assessing, and Reporting.

The Likert scale will be used to rate the responses.

Numerical Value	Verbal Description	Mean Score Ranges
5	Very Sensitive	4.20-5.00
4	Sensitive	3.40-4.19
3	Moderately Sensitive	2.60-3.39
2	Slightly Insensitive	1.80-2.59
1	Very Insensitive	1.00-1.79

The research instrument was modified by the researcher based on the components and performance standards (CB-PAST) and subjected to validity and reliability tests.

Data Gathering Procedures

The target respondents were to be surveyed using the research instruments, and permission was sought from the office of academic affairs at one state college. And after the grant of the permit, the researcher emulated the questionnaire as well as undertook the survey. The college research team assisted with said instrument's operation. The questionnaires were retrieved, and the data were aggregated, collated, analyzed, and interpreted given the study's specific problem.

All computation was done using the spreadsheet and Windows-based SPSS.

Validity of Data Collection Instruments

The researcher adopted the standards created for the evaluation survey questionnaire outlined by Good and Scates to examine the research instrument's validity.

Multiple examiners who were considered experts in the field of education were shown the developed research tool. They assessed the suitability and appropriateness of the questions by going through the research instrument item

by item. Improvement suggestions or recommendations were taken into consideration and using Good and Scates' criteria, the experts rated the instruments with a mean score of 3.70, interpreted as Very Good

Reliability of the Questionnaire

Reliability serves as a gauge for the research instrument's internal consistency (World Health Organization, 2005). A data collection tool is deemed reliable if it can collect reliable, consistent data from the respondents.

After the aforementioned instrument's dry run, the data was processed to perform a reliability analysis using Cronbach's alpha, which is employed whenever the researcher has items that cannot simply be classified as right or wrong. Thirty individuals took part in the research using the instrument; the above individuals weren't considered to be the study's actual informants Cronbach's used to assess the instrument's dependability, and the result of 0.986 was interpreted.

Statistical Tools

Problem 1 used the *Mean* to find out how the students at one state college feel about the degree of gender sensitivity in physical education courses both as a whole and when they were grouped according to sex. Problem 2 used a *t-test* to analyze the results and ascertain whether there was any statistically significant difference in the students' perceived degree of sensitivity when they were grouped according to sex.

With a qualified statistician's aid, data results were computed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Their responses were tabulated and analyzed using a spreadsheet and window-based SPSS to gauge the degree to which gender sensitivity exists in physical education as a whole.

The table below provides a summary of the overall mean scores as well as the scores for each aspect

Table 3. As a whole. The mean value of both males and females on gender sensitivity is shown in the following aspects:

Aspects	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description
Learners	212	4.16	0.11	Sensitive
Curriculum Content and Pedagogy	212	4.17	0.12	Sensitive
Planning, Assessing, and Reporting	212	4.29	0.004	Very sensitive
Grand mean	212	4.19	0.004	Sensitive

The table shows that both males and females received a mean score of 4.19, indicating that they are sensitive in their physical education class as a whole. This demonstrates that both genders receive equal learning support in their PE class. Additionally, all students' varied needs are met. Penney (2002) elaborates on this, declaring that many educators have been trained to believe that education is impartial and apolitical. As Bennett reminds us, education is neither neutral nor political. Every facet and culture of the educational process, along with every decision made for

educational reform at any level of education that takes into account someone's socialized worldview and cultural alignment, must be reviewed and restructured to foster truly multicultural classrooms and schools.

Both males and females were gender sensitive in their physical education class, as evidenced by their mean score of 4.17. This indicates that those students, regardless of gender, were active and participatory. Furthermore, the teacher's classroom techniques and sports activities are perceived as appropriate by the students and address the needs of both sexes. This refutes the findings of Murphy, Dionigi, & Litchfield (2014), which discovered that teachers' perceptions that lads are naturally more physically strong but also predominate through physical education and girls often exhibit innate weakness and subservience due to classroom instruction that mimics specific social edifices of sexual preference. The issue is not with teachers' awareness of gender issues but rather with how they tend to observe how some students influence others, and the methods they use or neglect to deal with it. Furthermore, Hannon & Williams (2008) states that males believed that females weren't working hard enough in class, while females thought that males weren't being cooperative enough.

Both males and females obtained a mean score of 4.17 for the curriculum, content, and pedagogy aspects of physical education class, with a verbal interpretation of sensitivity. This assumes that the teacher's approaches and methodologies address and suit the needs and intelligence of all students, regardless of their gender. Additionally, it sought ideas and contributions from both men and women. Contrary to what Scantlebury et al., (2007) claimed, girls and boys in classrooms have different educational experiences. The majority of participants prefer to learn in groups through practical activities, and target students may well dominate lecture-style classes. Female students, in particular, despise lectures, handouts, and "clogged" work assignments, preferring to study subjects relevant to their daily lives. But many instances, in the classroom and performance-based evaluations, girls take on passive roles. Girls read the instructions and record the results, whereas boys use the tools and complete the tasks.

The planning, assessing, and reporting results in physical education class showed a mean score of 4.29 with a verbal interpretation of "very sensitive" for both males and females, which is highly significant to note. It implies that the students believe the educator addressed the learning difficulties posed by both sexes. Correspondingly, to ensure that gender-sensitive standards and language were properly used, the educator used conventional assessment techniques and authentic learning. Contrary to what Scott (n.d.) asserted, many girls, even those who are intelligent and physically active, prefer individual, creative, as well as cooperative activities to an excessively competitive learning environment. The finding is frequently that ineffective provision can undermine such healthy practices, although lifelong physical activity habits are strongly supported by positive physical education experiences. However, it must be acknowledged that educational institutions in general and sports education, in particular, continues to perform a crucial facet of strengthening initiatives and sports development.

Table 4 shows the level of gender sensitivity in Physical Education Classes as perceived by students when taken according to sex.

Aspects	Male			Female		
	N	Mean	Verbal Description	N	Mean	Verbal Description
Learners	55	4.24	Very Sensitive	157	4.08	Sensitive
Curriculum and Pedagogy	55	4.25	Very Sensitive	157	4.08	Sensitive
Planning, Assessing, and Reporting	55	4.24	Very Sensitive	157	4.25	Very Sensitive
Grand Mean		4.25	Very Sensitive		4.14	Sensitive
Deviation		0.005			0.097	

Table 4 reflects that the grand mean of males as a whole is 4.25 with verbal interpretation very sensitive. On the other hand, Females obtained a means score of 4.14 which was verbally interpreted as sensitive. It implies that males are more gender-sensitive than females. The study of Beasley (2006) claims that males received significant attention in physical education, which contrasts this.

Participants accepted gender stereotypes and believed that men were the more aggressive and physically dominant gender. While the observation that females in their PE class exhibit sensitivity (Murphy, Dionigi, & Litchfield, 2014), Female students, in particular, are conceivably more inclined to take part in physical education (PE) and to make a positive impression if they feel supported and at ease around their male peers.

In the aspect of learners, males got the mean score of 4.24 and females 4.08 with a verbal interpretation of very sensitive and sensitive; respectively. This implies that both males and females are active and participative regardless of sex. Likewise, classroom techniques and activities employed by the teacher are perceived by both sexes as appropriate. This is supported by the Physical education fosters friendship, which claims (Wilhelmsen, 2012). not just the participant's best friend was selected to play; other friends as well. Both classmates and friends from the same school as well as relatives and friends from other schools made up this group of playmates. The importance of playing with other kids despite their differences was emphasized by the students in particular. The dynamic psychosocial chain of events that friendships go through as they are formed, established, and grown together is what is meant by the term "building friendship." This is not supported by the findings of Yungblut, Schinke, and McGannon (2012). It also demonstrates that there is compelling existing evidence within and elsewhere. Female youth face a variety of challenges, which may make regular exercise difficult for them.

In terms of curriculum content, and pedagogy aspect of their physical education class, the mean score obtained by males is 4.25 with an interpretation of very sensitive while the female obtained a mean score of 4.08 with an interpretation of sensitivity. Regardless of sex, approaches/ methodologies in teaching and activities provided by the teacher address are suited to learners' intelligence. Further, Ideas/contributions of both males and females are both solicited. Compare this to (Piña-Watson et al., 2016), which found whānau (Male modeling) groupings will become particularly effective in this regard as pedagogical processes in the "teaching model." As a result, along with other learning contexts in the physical education courses, they incorporated elements as "guiding principles" in their classroom instruction across the curriculum. Additionally, this is in contrast to Bailey, Wellard, and Dismore, (2005), which claims that many girls, including the smartest and most athletic ones, prefer independent, artistic, or collaborative activities to an excessively competitive learning environment. Even though having a good physical education experience is remarkably helpful for developing perpetual exercise habits, not having enough of it can compromise these beneficial routines.

In planning, assessing, and reporting in a physical education class, males showed a mean score of 4.24 and females 4.25, both with a verbal interpretation of very sensitive. Students feel that learning difficulties of both sexes are addressed by the teacher. Authentic learning and traditional assessment were utilized by the teacher to ensure that gender-sensitive criteria and gender-neutral language were properly observed. This is in line with findings on physical education from Everhart and Pemberton (2001), that show that, despite the presence of mixed classes, it can be challenging to compare the performance of boys and girls because it is graded differently. Additionally, grades don't just reflect performance because teachers also consider how much effort and progress students have made. It has been discovered that boys get better grades than girls. Further evidence for this comes from Women's Health Victoria (2010). Gender-specific strategies are required to ensure that both men and women get the most out of physical activity, which is critical for both genders' health.

Table 5. Difference of both sexes on the degree of gender sensitivity in Physical Education Classes among students of One State College.

Sex	N	Mean	SD	T	t-critical	Remark
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M	55	4.14	0.005	-0.622	1.97	No significance
F	157	4.25	0.097			

Table 5. The t-value is -0.622, which is higher than the tabular value of -1.97. This implies that when students are grouped according to sex, there is no discernible difference in the degree of gender sensitivity among them in PE classes. Thus, the data lend support to the study's hypothesis.

This indicates that among students at one state college, the respondents' perceptions of the degree of gender sensitivity in physical education classes are not significantly different from one another. This is supported by a study (London, Downey, Romero-Canyas, Rattan, & Tyson, 2012) on gender awareness in a medical curriculum, which discovered that when gender differences were recognized, the differences between the groups were indistinguishable.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Students are gender-sensitive to those of the opposite sex, according to research on how gender sensitivity is perceived by them in physical education classes at one state college. They are sensitive enough to allow both sexes equal freedom to express themselves and gain respect from their environment, not because they are exposed to the situation of a co-ed or mixed-class environment.

Additionally, they help one another meet their needs for development and growth. Although the sample size of this study results may be taken into consideration, it is safer to argue that reducing gender disparities in Physical Education classes will give opportunities for both genders to learn, compete, and have fun on equal ground.

Additionally, it should be mentioned that a participant in a state college PE program's gender schema may be influenced by the teacher's perception of gender sensitivity. For students to internalize and seize these opportunities, the teacher must be sensitive to gender issues and provide them with equal opportunities in all facets of their lives.

It can also be noted that the gender schema of NONESCOST PE students relies on the teacher's perception of gender sensitivity. If the teacher is gender-sensitive, he/she could provide equal opportunities in all aspects of the student's life which

The following recommendations are suggested:

1. The administration could allow on-campus activities that will foster awareness of gender sensitivity such as debate, essay writing, and information drive on gender equality.
2. The administration may take a closer look at the classroom-based gender equality problems for it is where the teaching-learning process takes place.
3. For faculty, staff, and students to serve as gender-responsive community agents, the administration may also conduct capability training on gender and development.
4. To increase awareness and gender sensitivity, the college might publish a news item on gender-related issues and VAWCS (violence against women and children) concerns.
5. Integration of the value of professionalism of gender and development in the curriculum could be.
6. Review of syllabi and instructional materials used in teaching Physical Education and other subjects.
7. Physical education Teachers could create a positive and gender-responsive learning environment that promotes equality and fun.
8. The results of this study should be supported or refuted by similar studies in a few academic disciplines.

The faculty should be assisted because the study's findings indicate that students are gender sensitive. When the teacher provides comparable opportunities for both sexes, gender differences or biases are reduced.

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